

COMMUNITY BASED APPROACHES TO RESILIENCE: RESPONSE TO VULNERABILITY OF COASTAL HABITAT IN CHANGING CLIMATE

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ABSTRACT

The coastal zone of Bangladesh is generally perceived to be a zone of multiple vulnerabilities. The people of that area are familiar with these natural activities, but recently climate change phenomenon adding fuel to these natural disasters. Although the death toll from cyclone event has been decreasing in recent years by constructing cyclone shelter and improving early warning systems, cyclones continue to put heavy burdens on the socio-economic life of Bangladesh. Coastal habitat and livelihood of the people are severely damaged because of natural hazards and climate change. However, these seems to be lack of overall solutions of livelihood with planned settlements for building disaster resilient community in hazard exposed areas. This research recognizes local resources and indigenous knowledge is a domain, which provides physical, social and financial capacity of coastal people towards community resilience. Indigenous communities living in the coastal areas for centuries have a unique cultural identity based on a close contact with nature. It is assumed that they have developed an indigenous perception of natural hazards and, thereby, possess effective survival strategies. The research also argues that community approaches to disaster management is essential for the adaptation of coastal people to take effective actions to reduce losses, damages and sufferings caused by climate change.

Introduction

The coastal zone of Bangladesh is generally perceived to be a zone of multiple vulnerabilities. Last 200 years at least 70 major cyclones hit the coastal belt of Bangladesh and during the last 35 years nearly 900,000 people died due to catastrophic cyclones. However, varying extents of disastrous natural events regularly occur in Bangladesh and the people of the country are familiar with these natural activities, but recently the climate change phenomenon adding fuel to these natural disasters. Extreme weather events are increasing in terms of frequency and intensity in the changing climate. These include: floods, cyclone, storm surges and salinity intrusion, river erosion, and droughts. Although there is no rigorous scientific evidence that tropical storms in the Bay of Bengal are increasing in frequency and intensity, the coastal people perceive an increased number of cyclones over the past few years. Although the death toll from cyclone event has been decreasing in recent years by organizing CPP (Cyclone Preparedness Program) like, constructing cyclone shelter and improving early warning systems, cyclones continue to put heavy burdens on the socio-economic life of Bangladesh.

The sectors which are severely damaged because of natural hazards and climate change are coastal habitat and livelihood of the people. However, these seems to be lack of overall solutions of livelihood with planned settlements for building disaster resilient community in hazard exposed areas. Livelihood and settlement in the coastal areas tends to focus more on the physical improvement with little attention to the socioeconomic issues of the community. Climate variability and change are predicted to impact on coastal habitat and local communities who are dependent on natural resources.

This research argues that community based approaches is an integral part of the strategy and policy for the

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development of community people to disaster risk reduction in changing climate. This research recognizes that local resources and indigenous knowledge is a domain, which provides physical, social and financial capacity of coastal people towards community resilience. Community approaches to disaster management is essential for the adaptation of coastal people to take effective actions to reduce losses, damages and sufferings caused by climate change. Through the experiences of natural disasters the local people have developed several strategies to survive and protect their houses and other valuable belongings. It is assumed that they have developed an indigenous perception of natural hazards and, thereby, possess effective survival strategies. They have inherited the time-tested experiences of generations internalized through a process of socialization. The anonymous local builders show a unique talent for setting their houses with natural surroundings and house-building techniques, including planning for every detail of construction, which is surprising to tackle the cyclone attack.

Research Methodology

To achieve the objective, the research will adopt the following strategy:

Literature review: A critical review of contemporary relevant literature on the body of knowledge that the research is premised upon.

Case Studies: To structure the investigation, the research will be based on the case study approach having diversified characteristics of coastal habitat and execution of local resource and indigenous knowledge by the community people.

Human Settlement with focus on Coastal Settlement in Bangladesh

Characteristics of coastal area adds a significant dimension in the settlement research and is becoming a research interest in the field of disaster management, development studies, built environment planning and design to examine the scope and possibilities of development to adapt with the changes. Very limited studies have been conducted on form and feature of disaster resilience human settlement.

There are few literatures that describe the pattern and form of coastal settlement in Bangladesh and how the local factors influence it. A research report by World Bank (2010) is an important source that describes the coastal settlement pattern in general. Linear settlements have been found along the coastal embankments, especially on the islands, and along the roadsides and riverbanks in the eastern districts. Other patterns of human settlements in the coastal areas include nucleated, scattered/ dispersed, and mixed type settlements.

The settlement of coastal areas is mostly influenced by geographical and geological characteristics, natural disaster (especially cyclone, storm surge and tidal surge) and livelihood pattern of the people. But livelihood patterns throughout the coastal belt in Bangladesh are not similar, such as, the people of Chittagong coast mostly depend on fishing rather than agriculture, because soil of these area is not fertile enough for good yield of crops. On the other hand, soil of coastal areas near Meghna estuarine is very fertile, so agriculture is more preferable livelihood for the people of these areas. The significant features of settlement in the coastal areas of Bangladesh are as follows:

- a) Houses on raised plinth.
- b) Surrounded by coastal green belt (especially by Mangrove forest)
- c) Coastal embankment.
- d) Killa for cattle (raised earthen platform for safety from tidal surge)
- e) Killa both for cattle and human
- f) Cyclone shelter, etc.

Present Status of Coastal Habitat in response to Natural Disaster

There are few literatures that describe the pattern and form of coastal settlement in Bangladesh and how the local factors influence it. The settlement of coastal areas is mostly influenced by geographical and geological characteristics, natural disaster (especially cyclone, storm surge and tidal surge) and livelihood pattern of the people. People in the coastal areas of Bangladesh are mostly depends on natural resources. But livelihood patterns throughout the coastal belt in Bangladesh are not similar, such as, the people of Chittagong coast mostly depend on fishing rather than agriculture, because soil of these area is not fertile enough for good yield of crops. On the other hand, soil of coastal areas near Meghna estuarine is very fertile, so agriculture is more preferable livelihood for the people of these areas.

Evaluation the impact of 1991 Cyclone: Urir Char Project 1985

Urir char located in the Meghna estuary was devastated by a severe cyclonic surge on the night of May 24, 1985, inflicting serious loss of life and property. There after a national committee was formed by the government for making recommendations of appropriate settlements planning for the area. Baqee (2011) reported that the Urir char settlement has remarkably passed its first field test by withstanding fury of 1991 cyclone storm with no loss of life and property. The author observed that after 6 years of completion of the project the houses the homesteads, the clusters, the village and even the central community zone has grown exactly the way it was conceived by the designer.

Field Survey on Housing at 1991's Cyclone Affected Areas

With this objective German Red Cross initiated a survey and study through us which resulted into a published report titled "BATTLING THE STORM" STUDY ON CYCLONE RESISTANT HOUSING. This study was conducted in six different locations of Cox's Bazar. The survey was based on the premise that problems in housing should not be defined by experts only but should be based on the dialogue with local people of the target areas. A direct involvement of the local people in problem identification was ensured, so local perceptions, attitude, values, shared knowledge etc. could be taken into account.

Field Survey and Study on SIDR Affected Areas, December 2007

Within a week after the cyclone, many development and humanitarian agencies together with the Government established the Shelter Coordination Group or the Shelter Cluster. An Early Recovery Assessment was carried out (within three months) followed by the Early Recovery Action plan, which emphasised the need to build Transitional or Core Family Shelters and to assist in repairing the houses.

Recommendation

To build a resilient community to combat with extreme natural events or to get rid from poverty it is required to develop the socio-economic condition. And to develop the socio-economic condition, concentration should be given on the following issues **a.** way to build a resilient habitat, **b.** scope of alternative and supplemental livelihood suitable for the community, and **c.** way to integrate livelihood with housing and settlement for increased income.

Approaches:

1. Empowerment of community people:

Local communities have their own coping and survival strategies to respond to any incidents long before any outside support would arrive. They are interested in protecting themselves from climate risks through community-based disaster preparedness and mitigation. However, empowering communities toward the use of technologies and viable adaptation practices for better management of climate change risks is essential for further improving livelihood adaptation and enhanced community resilience. To empower local communities it is necessary to work on four key areas, these are:

- a. Social action: Access to government policy and services and fighting against corruption.
- b. Governance and accountability issues: Representation in local level institutions.
- c. Economic action: Establishing rights over natural resources such as khas land and open water body.
- d. Gender issues: Establishment of women's rights and empowerment.

2. Building a resilient settlement through active participation of community people:

a. Settlement and land use planning to resist cyclone hazard: Coastal afforestation and construction of embankment are two planned measures should be adopted to protect the human settlement from sea born hazards. Inventory of safe havens, connection between different units inside the community and the outer places with roads network and proper drainage should be considered regarding settlement pattern. Land use patterns of a place need to be analysed prioritizing safe habitations, areas with potential resources and future extension of different functions. Hazardous areas need to be avoided of vulnerable practices like habitation, school and hospital locations. Infrastructures outside embankments should be discouraged by all means.

b. Coastal mangrove afforestation: As a measure of planned adaptation, the forest department of Bangladesh Govt. had implemented mangrove afforestation along the shoreline of coastal areas at Sitakundu. Experiment shows that the mangrove plantations along the coast are playing an important role in reducing the impact of cyclones and accompanying surges. It has been estimated that a 100 - 200 m wide mangrove belt

reduces wave heights by 20 to 25% (Islam, 2004). Mangrove plantation also helps in land maturation and makes the land suitable for human settlement.

Figure 1: Plan and Section of coastal Mangrove forest for a safer settlement

c. Semi-hard embankment: The embankment acts as first line of defence to dissipate the energy of cyclonic wave and prevent surge water to get inside. Apart from that, the road cum embankment is constructed above regular surge level and mostly remained inundation free in past years. This facilitates uninterrupted communication and provides shelter for the refugee during post disaster period. As a measure of protection, however, the effectiveness of embankment is not unquestioned. The height, width and slope of the embankment should be maintained properly and should be guided with proper vegetation to protect erosion.

Figure 2: A safer settlement with Mangrove forest, embankment and plantation

3. Using indigenous knowledge to build durable houses:

The houses in the coastal areas need to be hazard resilient so that least damaged of the structures and assets occurred due to tropical cyclone, and the dwellers always do not have to evacuate to cyclone shelters. These should be easy to construct and repair, cost effective and durable. Lightweight structures, especially older buildings with deteriorated condition are the most vulnerable to cyclones. Identifying indigenous technology and shared knowledge of the communities in home building will be effective in cyclone resistance. And combining local knowledge with easily applicable intervention of appropriate technology might be able to contribute towards the destruction of houses.

Figure 3: Hazard resilient indigenous houses

4. Upgrading the living standard of inhabitants by providing diversified livelihood:

Livelihood diversification is a process by which rural families construct a diverse portfolio of activities and social support capabilities in their struggle for survival and in order to improve their standard of living (Ellis, 1998). People attempt to diversify their income portfolios into both on- and off-farm activities in response to a risk, when primary activities fail to satisfy their subsistence needs (Hussein and Nelson, 1999). Datta *et al.* (2003) expand this notion in the context of Bangladesh.

Basically there are two ways to upgrade the living standard of inhabitants by providing diversified livelihood.

- a. Integrated Homestead Farming (IHF): Meeting the need of year-round income generating activities
- b. Intervene the financial capacity of community people through appropriate and alternative livelihood.

In this section, it has been tried to find out different types of alternative and supplementary livelihood (as diversified livelihood) which are suitable for the coastal settlement. These alternative and supplemental livelihoods can be cope by the local community within the homestead as well as in the settlement. So that it is also necessary to integrate the livelihood and the habitat for this kind of diversification.

Figure 4: A DRH with Integrated Homestead Farming

5. Capacity building through training, monitoring and evaluation:

Regular training, monitoring and evaluation is necessary for local communities to establish their own learning and action platforms to increase their understanding and ability to diagnose social issues that play an important role in mainstreaming and up-scaling climate risk management and potential adaptation options.

Conclusion

From the overall discussion and recommendation it is found that to build a resilient community, it is necessary to consider the above mentioned aspects. A strong house or a cyclone shelter solely cannot protect the coastal settlement from extreme weather events. To do this it is also required to make them economically self-sustained. Home based and community based alternative and sustainable livelihood approaches can provide an opportunity to increase their income level and reduce poverty and vulnerability. So that we have to provide sustainable income generating activities with disaster resilient habitat, both in the household level and community level.

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